

Integrating Genetic Engineering Techniques & Advanced Molecular Biology Approaches in DNA Analysis, Recombination Technology, and PCR

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ABSTRACT

The experiments conducted encompass critical techniques and principles central to genetic engineering and molecular biology. These include the isolation and analysis of plasmid DNA and the estimation of DNA concentration through the diphenylamine reaction. Advanced methodologies such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification, and gel electrophoresis analysis were employed to ensure accurate detection, quantification, and characterization of nucleic acids. Additionally, experiments on recombinant DNA technology were conducted, integrating principles of restriction enzyme digestion, ligation, and transformation to elucidate the mechanisms of genetic recombination. The studies culminated in a comprehensive understanding of molecular techniques pivotal for advancements in biotechnology.

Keywords: Genetic Engineering, Molecular Biology, Plasmid DNA, Recombination DNA Technology, Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), Gel Electrophoresis.

INTRODUCTION

Genetic Engineering & Molecular Biology form the foundation of modern biotechnology, which helps us in manipulating and analysing genetic material for various applications. These 20 experiments are a framework of genetic research & molecular engineering. Isolation and analysis of plasmid DNA provide a foundation for gene cloning and vector-based experimentation while the estimation of DNA concentration through diphenylamine reaction underscores the importance of quantitative analysis in molecular studies. Recombinant DNA technology, facilitated by restriction enzyme digestion, ligation, and transformation, showcases the ability to create and study novel genetic constructs.

The isolation and analysis of plasmid DNA, a foundational step in molecular biology, serve as an entry point to understanding gene cloning and vector-based applications. Plasmids, small circular DNA molecules, are crucial carriers of genetic information, widely used in recombinant DNA technology. By isolating plasmid DNA, researchers gain the ability to study genetic sequences, introduce novel genes into host organisms, and drive innovations in gene therapy and synthetic biology. This experiment emphasizes not only technical proficiency but also the significance of plasmids in biotechnological advancements. Quantitative analysis of DNA, exemplified by the diphenylamine (DPA) reaction, underscores the critical role of precise measurement in molecular studies.

Another cornerstone of genetic engineering is the synthesis of complementary DNA (cDNA) through reverse transcription. This process involves converting RNA templates into DNA, enabling researchers to study gene expression profiles and construct libraries of expressed genes. cDNA synthesis is integral to understanding cellular processes, identifying disease markers, and developing therapeutic interventions. By mastering this technique, researchers can unravel the complexities of gene regulation and harness this knowledge for practical applications.

The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) represents a technological leap in molecular biology, allowing for the exponential amplification of specific DNA sequences. PCR is indispensable in diagnostics, forensic science, and genetic research, offering unparalleled sensitivity and specificity. This experiment provides a hands-on introduction to PCR, enabling participants to understand its principles, optimize reaction conditions, and interpret amplification results. The widespread adoption of PCR underscores its transformative impact on molecular biology and its role in driving scientific discovery.

Gel electrophoresis, a technique for separating nucleic acids based on size, serves as a complementary tool to PCR and other molecular methods. By visualizing DNA fragments, researchers can verify the outcomes of experiments, assess the quality of nucleic acid samples, and identify genetic variations. Agarose gel electrophoresis, in particular, is a staple of molecular biology labs, offering a straightforward yet powerful means of analyzing DNA. This experiment reinforces the importance of visualization techniques in genetic research.

Recombinant DNA technology, encompassing restriction digestion, ligation, and transformation, showcases the ability to create and study novel genetic constructs. Restriction enzymes, molecular "scissors," enable precise cutting of DNA at specific sequences, laying the

groundwork for genetic recombination. Ligation, the process of joining DNA fragments, and transformation, the introduction of recombinant DNA into host cells, are pivotal steps in creating genetically modified organisms (GMOs). These techniques have broad implications, from developing disease-resistant crops to producing biopharmaceuticals.

The screening of transformed colonies, using methods such as X-gal and IPTG, further highlights the intricacies of recombinant DNA technology. These techniques allow researchers to identify successful transformations and evaluate the expression of introduced genes. This experiment demonstrates the practical aspects of genetic engineering, bridging theoretical knowledge with real-world applications. The ability to manipulate genetic material with precision has far-reaching consequences, driving advancements in medicine, agriculture, and industrial biotechnology.

The ligation process, a critical step in constructing recombinant DNA, exemplifies the precision and ingenuity required in genetic engineering. By joining DNA fragments to form functional constructs, researchers can create novel genetic combinations, paving the way for innovations in synthetic biology and gene therapy. This experiment underscores the importance of meticulous technique and a deep understanding of molecular interactions in achieving successful outcomes.

Southern blotting, a method for detecting specific DNA sequences, illustrates the integration of molecular biology techniques for targeted analysis. This technique involves transferring DNA from a gel onto a membrane, followed by hybridization with labeled probes. Southern blotting is invaluable for gene mapping, mutation analysis, and identifying genetic variations. This experiment emphasizes the role of hybridization-based methods in advancing our understanding of genetic material.

ISOLATION AND ANALYSIS OF PLASMID DNA

1 ABSTRACT

Isolation and analysis of plasmid DNA involve extracting small, circular DNA molecules from bacterial cells. This process includes breaking the cells, separating plasmid DNA from other cell components, purifying it and analyzing DNA using methods like gel electrophoresis. This is important for studying genes and biotechnological applications.

1.1 PRINCIPLE

Bacterial cells are lysed to release their contents. Then, proteins and chromosomal DNA are removed using chemical treatments. Plasmid DNA remains in the solution due to its small, circular structure. The plasmid is purified through precipitation or column based techniques. Lastly it is analyzed using methods like gel electrophoresis to confirm its size.

1.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENTS REQUIRED

Components	Description
Ethidium Bromide	Staining dye used to stain DNA in gel electrophoresis to identify and visualize the DNA bands under UV illumination
Luria Bertani medium	Medium to culture bacterial cells
Autoclaved sigma water	The sigma water produced by sigma-Aldrich is used for laboratory purposes its autoclaved to eliminate contaminants and maintain purity
Agarose and buffers for gel electrophoresis	Separation of nucleic acid fragments based on size and visualize the resulting bands under UV illumination
Bacterial culture	<i>E. coli</i> bacterial culture (Dh5 α)
Resuspension solution	To resuspend the cells after centrifugation for lysis of cells
Lysis solution	It is an alkaline solution used to lyse the cell membrane to release DNA from cell
Neutralising solution	For neutralizing the lysate after cell lysis
Silica columns	The columns made of silica selectively binds to plasmid DNA.
Wash solution	To eliminate the contaminants from pure DNA
Elution solution	Removal of plasmid DNA to isolate pure plasmid DNA

Equipment's	Description
Autoclave	It is machine used for sterilization of laboratory equipment's and media under high pressure and temperature.
Incubate shaker	It is a laboratory equipment to incubate the samples at specific temperature and shake speed
Microcentrifuge tube	Used to store the samples, centrifugation and mixing of samples
Horizontal electrophoresis apparatus	A laboratory equipment used to separate the DNA fragments based on size under the influence of electric current
Power supply unit	Provides electric current to make negatively charged DNA migrate through positively charged end of the gel
Gel documentation or trans illuminator	An UV light source that illuminates the DNA to visualize DNA bands
Micro pipettes (P1000, P200, P20).	To transfer and mixing the mixtures

1.3 PROTOCOL

Day 1: Culture of bacterial cells

Description : Inoculate 50ul of bacterial culture in 5ml LB medium. Allow the cells to grow overnight at 37°C at 200rpm.

DAY 2: Isolation of Plasmid DNA

Description : Centrifuging the sample

Procedure: Transfer 1.5ml broth containing cells into microcentrifuge tube and centrifuge the sample at 13000rpm for 1min. discard the supernatant

Description: Resuspension of pellet

Procedure: Resuspend the pellet in 200ul of resuspension solution and mix it with pipette

Description: Lysis of cell

Procedure:

- Add 200ul of lysis solution and invert gently. Allow to clear for 5min
- Add 350 ul of neutralisation solution and mix it for 5-6 times
- Centrifuge the sample at 13000rpm for 10 min. discard the pellet cause it contains cellular debris and retain the supernatant which contains plasmid DNA

Description: Separation of plasmid DNA through column based method

Procedure:

- Add 500ul of column preparation solution to binding column in a collection tube
- Spin at 13000 rpm for 1min and discard the flow through.
- Transfer the clear lysate to binding column and centrifuge at 13000rpm for 1min. discard the flow through.

- Add 750ul of wash solution spin for 1min at discard the flow through
- Spin for 1min to dry the column at room temperature
- Transfer the column to new collection tube. Add 70ul of elution solution to the column . the purified plasmid DNA is released . store the eluate which contains the plasmid DNA at -20C or -30C.

Day 3: Agarose gel electrophoresis of isolated plasmid DNA

Description: Preparation of agarose solution

Procedure: Add 0.8% of agar to 1X TBE buffer

Description: Polymerization of gel

Procedure: Pour the prepared agarose solution into gel casting tray with combs. Allow it to polymerize and remove the combs carefully for formation of wells. Submerge the agarose gel in horizontal electrophoresis tank containing 1X TBE buffer.

Description: Loading the DNA sample

Procedure:

- Take the 5ul of eluate which consists of plasmid DNA and add 2ul of sample Buffer
- Load 7ul of DNA in each well along with it load DNA ladder in one of the wells

Description: Connection to power supply

Procedure: Place the gel in gel electrophoresis apparatus. Turn on the power supply. Run the gel with the dye tracking the progress of DNA.

Description: Staining the sample and visualizing the sample in UV light

Procedure: Remove the gel and place it in ethidium bromide solution. After staining the gel rinse it with water and place it on gel documentation or transilluminator to visualize the DNA under UV light.

SUMMARY OF THE PROCEDURE:

Day 1: Culture of bacterial cells

Day 2:

1. Centrifuging the sample
2. Resuspension of pellet
3. Lysis of cell
4. Separation of plasmid DNA through column based separation

Day 3:

1. Preparation of agarose solution
2. Polymerization gel
3. Loading the DNA sample
4. Connection to power supply

1.4 RESULTS

Figure (1.1)

Figure (2.2)

Figure (1.1) : LB media prepared in lab

Figure (1.2) : Indicates the isolated plasmid DNA.

ESTIMATION OF DNA THROUGH DIPHENYLAMINE (DPA) REACTION

2 ABSTRACT

Estimation of DNA using diphenylamine is one of the method to estimate the concentration of DNA. in this experiment diphenylamine is used to react with DNA under acidic conditions forming β dihydroxylevolinaldehyde which gives blue colour upon reaction with absorption maxima at 595nm. It involves preparation of all samples (standard diluted solution, blank and unknown solution) in triplicates Followed of addition of diphenylamine in each sample and incubate the samples in boiling water. Using spectrophotometer estimate the samples at absorbance 595nm.

2.1 PRINCIPLE

the concentration of DNA is determined using diphenylamine method using a spectrophotometer. The diphenylamine is organic compound with the formula $(C_6H_5)_2NH$. The compound is derivative of aniline consisting of amine bound to two phenyl groups. The DNA sample under acidic conditions it becomes depurated followed by dehydration of deoxyribose sugar of DNA into a blue component known as β dihydroxylevolinaldehyde. The intensity of blue colour determines the concentration of DNA. It is estimated by UV spectrometer in 595nm. Since only deoxyribose of purine nucleotides reacts the value obtained represents only half to total amount.

2.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENTS REQUIRED

Equipment's	Description
Spectrophotometer	A machine used quantification of DNA
Water bath	Incubation solutions
Test tubes	To mix the solutions, storage of samples and to heat a particular mixture
Pipettes	To transfer and mix the solutions
Graduated cylinder	To measure reagents, solutions and samples for DNA analysis

Components	Description
Standard DNA solution	The sample DNA used in experiment to estimate its concentration
Diphenylamine reagent	Reagent used to estimate the concentration of DNA
Saline citrate buffer	It is used for diluting the standard DNA sample and to maintain stable environment
Glacial acetic buffer	It acts as solvent for diphenylamine to dissolve it completely and form reagent solution

ethanal	It reacts with diphenylamine to form a coloured complex
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2.3 PROTOCOL

Day 1: Preparation of reagent

Description: Preparation of diphenylamine solution

Procedure:

- Dissolve 1.5g of diphenylamine reagent to 100ml of glacial acetic acid and add 1.5ml of conc H₂SO₄. Store the solution.
- On the day of use prepare ethanal solution in DH₂O. add 0.5ml of this solution to each 100ml of diphenylamine solution

Day 2: Quantification of standard DNA sample

Description: serial dilution of standard DNA sample and preparation of samples

Procedure:

- Serial dilution of standard DNA sample using saline citrate buffer.
- Prepare all the samples(standard solution, unknown solution, blank) in triplicates. for 2ml of each sample add 2ml of prepared diphenylamine reached to each sample.
- Incubate all the samples in water bath for 10minutes

Description: To read the absorbance of DNA sample using spectrophotometer

Procedure:

- Cool the samples and read the absorbance at 595nm against the blank.
- Construct a standard curve of absorbance A₅₉₅ vs. quantity of DNA, then calculate the concentration of unknown DNA dissolved in the saline citrate solution.
- Calculation: Determine the amount of DNA in the unknown sample by plotting a standard curve of A₅₉₅ on the Y-axis and µg of DNA on the X-axis.

2.4 SUMMARY OF THE PROCEDURE

Day 1: Preparation of reagent

Day 2:

1. Serial dilution of standard DNA sample and preparation of samples.
2. To read the absorbance of DNA sample using spectrophotometer.

2.5 RESULTS

Fig (2.1)

Fig (2.2)

Fig (2.3)

Fig (2.1): The prepared diphenylamine solution

Fig (2.2): Saline citrate buffer

Fig (2.3): The prepared samples with all concentration included DNA, water, Buffer & Etc

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF PLASMID DNA THROUGH GEL ELECTROPHORESIS

3 ABSTRACT

The isolated plasmid DNA can qualitatively estimated using gel electrophoresis method. Gel electrophoresis utilizes an agarose gel which is a polysaccharide to separate plasmid DNA into fragments based on size. It involves initially preparation of agarose solution and then polymerization by casting the gel into tray with combs to form wells. The isolated plasmid DNA sample along with DNA ladder are loaded into the wells with the help of pipette. The gel is stained with ethidium bromide for visualization. The gel is placed in gel electrophoresis apparatus and an electric current is applied causing negatively charged DNA (cathode) migrates toward positively charged electrode (anode). The DNA is separated based on size the molecule with higher molecular weight moves slowly while molecules with lower molecular weight travels fast. After electrophoresis the separated DNA fragments are visualised under UV transilluminator. The ethidium bromide binds to DNA and under UV light the bands become visible. Size of plasmid DNA is estimated by comparing the band pattern to the DNA ladder.

3.1 PRINCIPLE

Agarose gel electrophoresis is the most effective way of separating DNA fragments of varying sizes ranging from 100 bp to 25 kb. It estimates the quality of isolated plasmid DNA. Prior to the adoption of agarose gels, DNA was primarily separated using sucrose density gradient centrifugation, which only provided an approximation of size. Agarose gel used electrophoresis is made up of Agarose a polysaccharide which is isolated from seaweed gelidium and gracilaria. Agarose is the most common separating medium for large molecules of DNA by electrophoresis. The concentration of agarose in a gel will depend on the sizes of the DNA Fragments to be separated with agarose concentrations of 0.3–2% are mostly used. The polymerization of gel by heating the solution and let it cool for polymerize by casting gel in gel tray with combs to create wells. Total 8 wells are created after polymerization to load the DNA samples. In 1st well the DNA ladder is loaded. DNA ladder of 1kilobasepairs is used as standard for measuring the size of DNA. The gel is stained with ethidium bromide. Ethidium bromide is a intercalating dye this binds to DNA and fluoresces under UV light allowing the DNA fragments to be visualized. The more DNA present, the brighter the band. samples mixed with a loading dye are placed in one end of the gel which is immersed in running buffer. the agarose gel is placed in gel electrophoresis apparatus supplied with electric current. An electrical current is then passed through the gel by electrodes at each end of the gel tank. The negatively charged DNA migrates through agarose pores in response to electric current towards positively charged electrode (anode) with smaller fragments moving faster. After sufficient separation the gel is removed from gel tank and placed under UV transilluminator provided with the source of UV light. The ethidium bromide allows to visualize the separated bands of the sample and their size is determined by comparison to a DNA ladder with known band sizes. Agarose gel electrophoresis used to be the essential gel electrophoresis method for any molecular diagnostic laboratory due to its simple procedure, wide applicability, and inexpensive apparatus. Nucleic acids up to 50kbase can be separated by agarose gel electrophoresis.

3.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT'S REQUIRED

Components	Description
Agarose powder	It is used as separating medium to separate the DNA .
Tris- acetic acid EDTA(TAE buffer)	It is used as running buffer and for preparation of gels
DNA sample	It is isolated plasmid DNA to estimate its quality.
Deionise H2O	To wash the gel after electrophoresis

DNA loading dye	To stain the DNA sample
Ethidium bromide	A fluorescent dye used for staining and visualizing the DNA under UV light.

Equipment's	Description
Gel electrophoresis apparatus	To separate the DNA fragments based on size and electric current
Measuring cylinder	To measure the volume of liquids
UV transilluminator	Source of UV light

3.3 PROTOCOL

DAY 1: Preparation of gel

Description: Preparation of agarose solution using running buffer.

Procedure :

- Weigh the appropriate mass of agarose to be prepared. Add 0.3-0.2% of agar in 1/3 volume of flask of running buffer. Swirl to mix the solution.
- The most commonly used b running buffers are TAE buffers (40 mM Tris-acetate, 1 mM EDTA) and TBE buffers (45 mM Tris-borate, 1 mM EDTA).

Description: Melting the prepared agarose solution

Procedure: Melt the prepared agarose solution by heating it in microwave or Bunsen burner. At every 30seconds of interval remove the flask and Swirl the mixture. Repeat until the agarose is completely dissolved.

Description: Staining the gel

Procedure: Add 0.5ug/mL of Ethidium bromide to the gel. It can also be added after electrophoresis.

Description: Polymerization of gel

Procedure:

- Allow agarose to cool either on benchtop or incubation at 65°C in water bath.
- Place the gel tray into the casting apparatus. Alternately one can tape the open edges of the gel tray . Place the comb into the gel to create wells.
- Pour the molten agarose solution into the gel tray. Allow it to sit at room temperature. After polymerization of agarose gel remove the comb and place the gel into gel box. Store at 4C until use.

DAY 2: Setting up of Gel Apparatus and Separation of DNA Fragments

Description: Preparation of loading dye

Procedure:

- Gel loading dye is prepared at 6X concentration (0.25% bromophenol blue, 0.25% xylene cyanole, 30% glycerol). The prepared loading dye is added to DNA sample. It helps to track the DNA travelled through the agarose gel. Allows the gel to sink in the buffer.

Description: Loading the DNA sample

Procedure:

- Add same running buffer which was used to prepare the gel up to the surface of the gel
- Remove the lid of the gel box and carefully load the DNA samples and replace the lid.

Description: Connecting to power supply and running the gel

Procedure:

- Attach leads of the gel box to power supply. The cathode should be closer to wells than anode
- Check that the electrodes are plugged into correct slots in the power supply.
- Set the power supply to voltage (1-5V/cm between electrodes).
- Turn on the power supply
- Run the gel until the dye travels to appropriate distance.

Observing Separated DNA fragments

Description: Visualizing the DNA samples under the UV light

Procedure:

- After electrophoresis turn off the power supply and remove the lid of the gel box.
- Remove the gel from the gel tray and place the gel on the UV transilluminator to expose the gel to UV rays.
- DNA bands are observed as orange fluorescent bands.

3.4 RESULTS

Fig (3.1)

Fig (3.2)

Fig (3.3)

Fig (3.1): Gel placed in electrophoresis apparatus.
 Fig (3.2): Gel electrophoresis apparatus.
 Fig (3.3): DNA bands visualized under UV light.
 Lane 1: DNA ladder (1kb)
 Lane 2,3: Plasmid DNA Bands (Not visualised clearly)
 Lane 5,6: Plasmid DNA bands (Visualised clearly)

TO PERFORM COMPETENT CELL PREPARATION

4 ABSTRACT

Genetic engineering is the process of introducing foreign DNA into bacteria, which is done by making the cells competent. A description of preparing chemically competent *Escherichia coli* cells using calcium chloride treatment was given in this research paper. Being a vector for transformation, the cells can attract the DNA with a mutation, e.g., the required antibiotic resistance, by copulating with a plasmid.

4.1 PRINCIPLE

Competent cells are term which suppose bacterial cells treated in some particular way, so making them more capable to get from outside the DNA. Calcium chloride causes disruption of the cell wall, allowing the DNA to pass inside. These cells, after being taken in, can be used in the case of transformation experiments to introduce the desired genetic material into the host receptor.

4.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT

COMPONENTS	DESCRIPTION
Bacterial Strain	<i>Escherichia coli</i> DH5 α .

REAGENTS	DESCRIPTION
Luria Bertani (LB) broth	It helps the bacteria to grow.
0.1M MgCl ₂ and 0.1 M CaCl ₂	The solutions cause the cells to become more competent
Ampicillin	This is an antibiotic that is used in the period of selection

EQUIPMENTS	DESCRIPTION
laminar flow hood	Provides a sterile environment by filtering air to remove contaminants.
Incubator shaker	Combines incubation and shaking for optimal growth of cultures under controlled conditions
Autoclave	Sterilizes equipment and materials using high-pressure steam

4.3 PROTOCOL

Day 1: Preparation of Media and Reagents

- Preparation of LB agar
 - Description:** For culturing the cells
 - Procedure:** Prepare LB agar plates with a final concentration of 100 μ g/ml ampicillin. Sterilize the LB medium, and allow it to cool to 45°C, then pour approximately 20 ml into each plate. Let them solidify and store at 4°C.
- Prepare Calcium Chloride and Magnesium Chloride Solutions
 - Description:** Used to prepare competent cells.
 - Procedure:** Prepare 0.1 M CaCl₂ (500 ml) and 0.1 M MgCl₂ (500 ml), autoclave, and store at 4°C.

Day 2: Inoculation and Growth of E. coli Cells

3. Cell Inoculation:

- **Description:** To introduce cells into growth medium or host environment
- **Procedure:** Add 100 μ l of E. coli DH5 α from a frozen glycerol stock into 5 ml of LB medium. Incubate the culture overnight at 37°C with shaking at 200 rpm.

Day 3: Preparation of Competent Cells

4. Inoculation into New LB Medium

- **Description:** To promote bacterial growth under optimal nutrient conditions.
- **Procedure:** Add 1 ml of the overnight culture into 50 ml of new LB medium in a sterile conical flask. Culture is incubated at 37°C and 200 rpm until OD600 = 0.4-0.6 or for around 2 hours of incubation.

5. Harvesting Cells:

- **Description:** To collect cells from a culture typically through centrifugation
- **Procedure:** Cell culture is moved to ice for 10 minutes to cool the cells and then it is centrifuged at 4°C for 10 minutes at 4,000 rpm. Supernatant is discarded, and the pellet is gently suspended in 20 ml cold 0.1 M CaCl₂.

6. Competence preparation

- **Procedure:** Following resuspension, incubate the cells on ice for 30 minutes. This enables the cells to uptake calcium ions that will render their membranes permeable.

7. Second Centrifugation:

- **Description:** To collect the cells without any supernatant.
- **Procedure:** Centrifuge the cells at 4,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. Discard the supernatant.

8. Final Resuspension:

- **Description:** To get the pellet
- **Procedure:** Re-suspend the pellet gently in 1-2 ml of cold 0.1 M CaCl₂. Keep the suspension on ice until ready for use.

9. Storage:

- **Description:** For further process and store for long time
- **Procedure:** Dispense the re-suspended cells into aliquots of 200-300 μ l and store them at -80°C for long-term storage. Alternatively, they can immediately be used to transform

4.4 RESULTS

Fig (4.1) : shows preparation of competent cells, transformation taking place and recovery but plating.

TO PERFORM TRANSFORMATION OF DESIRED BACTERIAL STRAIN USING PLASMID DNA

5 ABSTRACT

Bacterial transformation is a fundamental molecular biology technique used to introduce plasmid DNA into a target bacterial strain, enabling genetic modification for various purposes. This process involves setting up competent cells, incubating them with plasmid DNA, and facilitating DNA uptake through heat shock or electroporation. Following transformation, the bacteria are grown on selective media to ensure the successful incorporation of the plasmid DNA. This method is widely used in cloning, protein expression, and genetic engineering, offering a reliable protocol for studying gene function and producing recombinant molecules.

5.1 PRINCIPLE

Transformation is the phenomenon whereby a bacterial cell absorbs exogenous DNA from the surrounding environment. In this experiment, competent *E. coli* cells prepared in the previous step are exposed to plasmid DNA. The competent cells take up the plasmid DNA, which often carries antibiotic resistance genes, under conditions that make the bacterial cell membrane more permeable, such as heat shock. The cells are then plated on agar plates containing an antibiotic, such as ampicillin, to select for transformed cells once the plasmid is inside the bacterial cells. Only those cells will survive and produce colonies that have successfully incorporated the plasmid DNA that carries a gene for resistance to the antibiotic.

5.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT

COMPONENTS	DESCRIPTION
Competent <i>E. coli</i> cells	<i>E. coli</i> DH5 α cells, prepared in the previous experiment.
Plasmid DNA	The plasmid that contains the gene of interest and an antibiotic resistance marker, for example, ampicillin resistance
SOC medium	Super Optimal broth with Catabolite repression medium for cell recovery.
LB agar plates	Containing the selective antibiotic (e.g., ampicillin) for colony growth
Incubator	For bacterial growth.
Water bath	Set at 42°C for heat shock.
Ice	To keep cells cold before heat shock
Micropipettes and tips	For transferring DNA and samples.
Sterile techniques	To avoid contamination

PROTOCOL

Day 1: Preparation of Competent Cells

1. Preparation of Competent Cells
 - **Description-** To make bacterial cells capable of taking up foreign DNA
 - **Procedure-** Thaw the competent E. coli cells on ice. Handle the cells gently to maintain their competence.
2. DNA Addition
 - **Description-** To introduce foreign DNA such as plasmid DNA into competent cells for transformation
 - **Procedure-** Add 1-10 µl of plasmid DNA to 200 µl of competent cells (typically 1-2 ng of plasmid DNA is used). Gently mix by pipetting up and down to ensure the plasmid is evenly distributed.
3. Incubation on Ice
 - **Description-** To stabilize the cell membrane and facilitate DNA uptake
 - **Procedure-** Incubate the DNA-cell mixture on ice for 30 minutes to allow the plasmid DNA to bind to the competent cells. This step helps the cells to take up the DNA efficiently during the heat shock.
4. Heat Shock
 - **Description-** To create a thermal imbalance allowing plasmid DNA to enter the competent cells.
 - **Procedure -** Add on a hot shower using water bath at 42°C for exactly 45 seconds to shock the cells placed in the tube. During the ice incubation, uptake of the plasmid DNA is induced by causing increased permeability of the cell membrane of the bacteria. Put the cells back onto the ice immediately for 2-5 minutes to revive and stabilize the cells in vitro. Add 800 µl of SOC medium (pre-warmed to 37°C) to the cells. This medium provides nutrients for the cells to recover and express the antibiotic resistance gene present on the plasmid. Incubate the cells at 37°C for 1 hour with shaking at 200 rpm to allow the cells to express the antibiotic resistance gene.
5. Plating on Selective Agar Plates
 - **Description-** To provide nutrients for successful incorporated the plasmid DNA to grow.
 - **Procedure-** Following the recovery period, spread 100-200 µl of the transformation mixture onto LB agar plates containing the selective antibiotic (e.g., ampicillin). Use a sterile spreader or sterile glass beads to spread the transformation mixture evenly across the plate. Cover the entire surface.

5.3 RESULT

Figure (5.1)

Figure (5.2)

Fig (5.1& 5.2) : Shows transformation with the competent cells

RESTRICTION DIGESTION OF PLASMID PHAGE DNA

6 ABSTRACT

Restriction digestion, also known as restriction endonuclease, is a fundamental technique in molecular biology that cleaves DNA at specific sites. This study aimed to perform restriction digestion on plasmid DNA, pUC19, and a viral genome from lambda phage using specific enzymes, EcoRI and Hind III. The fragments were then subjected to gel electrophoresis to confirm the specificity and efficiency of the enzymatic digestion. The endonucleases recognize specific palindromic sequences within the DNA, making the fragmentation predictable. PUC19 plasmid DNA with EcoRI yielded a single band, while Hind III digestion generated fragments revealing indicative cleavage sites. Lambda phage DNA yielded multiple bands due to its larger size and complex corresponding restriction maps. This study underscored the versatility of restriction digestion in molecular biology and contributed to advancements in research and biotechnology innovations.

6.1 PRINCIPLE

Restriction digestion is a method through which DNA is reduced at specific sequences with the usage of restriction enzymes. The limit enzymes apprehend unique palindromic sequences within the DNA and cleave it, reducing into fragments of various sizes. The method is widely utilized in molecular biology to control DNA for figuring out precise sequences, to put together DNA for similarly analysis that is probably cloning or sequencing, and so forth. In this test, plasmid DNA is digested with one or extra restrict enzymes. The fragments produced are then separated by way of agarose gel electrophoresis to verify the digestion efficiency and fragment length. Through assessment of the fragment sizes with the DNA ladder, we are able to decide the molecular weight of the plasmid and the range of restrict web sites in the DNA.

6.2 COMPONENT AND EQUIPMENT

Components	Description
Plasmid	pUC19 (or any other plasmid with a know restriction map).
Lambda Phage DNA	Genomic DNA of lambda phage.
Eco RI	Recognizes the sequence 5'-GAATTC-3' and cuts between G and A.
Hind III	Recognizes the sequence 5'-AAGCTT-3' and cuts between A and A.

Gel Electrophoresis Components	Description
Agarose Powder	To prepare a 1% agarose gel.
DNA Ladder	A molecular weight marker for estimating DNA fragment sizes.
Electrophoresis Gel Tray & Comb	To prepare the agarose gel for pouring.
Chamber & Power Supply	For running the gel.

Equipment	Description
UV Transilluminator	To detect the bands of DNA.
Micropipettes	1-10 μ L, 10-100 μ L, and 100-1000 μ L, for precise volume transfer of liquids.
Incubator or Water Bath	Set at 37°C, to carry out enzyme-catalysed reactions.
Refrigerator/Freezer	For storing enzymes and buffers.
Parafilm or Reaction Tubes	0.5 mL or 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes used for reaction setup.

Buffers and Solution	Description
10X Restriction	Specific buffer optimize for Eco RI and Hind III, containing Enzyme Buffer appropriate pH, salts and cofactors.(e.g. MgCl ₂)
0.5M EDTA	Used to stop the restriction digestion reaction by binding magnesium ion which is essential cofactors for restriction enzymes.
1X TAE Buffer	For preparing the agarose gel and running electrophoresis.
Ethidium Bromide	Staining agent for visualizing DNA under UV light
Nuclease-Free Water	For diluting and preparing reaction mixtures. (1 μ g/mL in gel).
6X Loading Dye	For tracking DNA migration during gel electrophoresis.

6.3 PROTOCOL

DAY1: Preparation of restriction digestion reaction mix for Puc18 and Lambda

Description: To prepare reaction mixture for PuC18 and lambda DNA digestion by incubation and stopping enzymatic activity.

Procedure: A clean 1.5ml microcentrifuge is taken and two reaction take place according to given table. And reagents were mixed and centrifuged briefly, tube was kept at 37 degree C FOR 4 hours. After to stop the reaction 1 microlitre of 0.5M EDTA was added.

pUC18 digestion		λ DNA digestion	
pUC18 plasmid (1ug/μl)	1	λ DNA	1
Hind III assay buffer (10X)	2	Hind III assay buffer (10X)	2
Hind III (10U/μl)	0.5	Hind III (10U/μl)	0.5
Eco R I (10U/μl)	0.5	Eco R I (10U/μl)	0.5
Sterile distilled water	16	Sterile distilled water	16
Total	20μl	Total	20μl

Note: For double digestion, Hind III buffer was used in which both EcoRI and Hind III will work because of the low salt concentration.

DAY2: Agarose Gel Electrophoresis for Digested DNA Analysis

1. Prepare 0.8% Agarose Solution in 1X TBE Buffer

Description: Agarose gel is a matrix that separates DNA fragments according to their size.

Procedure: Mix 0.8 g of agarose in 100 mL of TBE buffer. Boil until the agarose is completely dissolved and let it cool slightly before pouring into the casting tray.

2. Submerge the Gel

Description: To allow DNA migration it has to be put in TBE buffer

Procedure: Submerge the solidified gel in a horizontal electrophoresis tank containing 1X TBE buffer, which is the conductive medium for DNA migration.

3. Sample Preparation and Loading

Description: Mix DNA with loading dye and also load sample into gel wells

Procedure: Mix 5 μL of each DNA sample with 2 μL loading dye. Load 7 μL of the mix into the gel wells. Also, load a DNA ladder as a molecular size reference.

4. Run Electrophoresis

Description: To separate DNA fragments based on their sizes.

Procedure: Apply a constant voltage to the gel to separate DNA fragments. Smaller fragments migrate faster toward the positive electrode, while larger fragments move slower.

5. Staining with Ethidium Bromide

Description: To visualize DNA under UV

Procedure: After electrophoresis, immerse the gel in ethidium bromide solution for 30 minutes. The stain binds to DNA, making it visible under UV light.

6. Visualization

Description: Observe florescent DNA bands using UV transilluminator.

Procedure: Place the stained gel on a UV transilluminator or gel documentation system to view the DNA bands. Ethidium bromide fluoresces under UV, so DNA fragments are visible.

7. Quantification

Description: Compare the DNA bands

Procedure: To observed sample DNA to the DNA ladder to estimate fragment sizes. The intensity of the bands gives an approximation of DNA concentration.

6.4 SUMMARY TABLE OF PROCEDURE

DAY	STEP	PROCEDURE
Day 1	1	Preparation of buffer i.e. assay buffer
Day 1	2	Preparation of restriction digestion reaction
Day 2	3	Assemble the electrophoresis unit
Day 2	4	Preparation of 0.8%Agarose Gel
Day 2	5	Preparation the running buffer
Day 2	6	Sample preparation
Day 2	7	load sample into the wells
Day 2	8	Perform electrophoresis
Day 2	9	Staining with ethidium bromide
Day 2	10	Visualization and quantification

6.5 RESULTS

Fig (6.1)

Fig (6.1): Lane3- DNA Ladder as it serves as reference for comparing band sizes.

Lane5- Puc18 digestion as it has distinct fragment sizes corresponding to the plasmid digestion.

Lane 7- Lambda digestion as it shows bands characteristic of lambda DNA cleaved by specific restriction enzyme.

SCREENING OF TRANSFORMED COLONIES BY X GAL AND IPTG

7 ABSTRACT

This study looks at X-gal and IPTG and their application in screening for transformed colonies. This is achieved through the lacZ gene which encodes for the enzyme, β -galactosidase, and acts as a marker to differentiate between recombinant and non-recombinant colonies. X-gal is a chromogenic substrate that when acted on by β -galactosidase turns blue. Non recombinant colonies remain blue while the recombinant ones are white because the lacZ gene has been disrupted. This method is critical in the determination of which transformation events have been successful. As transformation is one of the most crucial processes in molecular biology since it enables the incorporation of foreign DNA into host organisms. X-gal and IPTG screening allows the identification of recombinant colonies in a simple and efficient manner. It aids the process by making it possible to use the lac operon system which marks the successful incorporation of foreign DNA which can later be useful in a variety of applications.

7.1 PRINCIPLE

The lacZ gene, most cloning vectors contain the gene which encodes β -galactosidase that hydrolyzes X-gal to form a blue product. This method enables one to tell the difference between recombinant and non-recombinant colonies. When lacZ gene containing plasmids are introduced into competent cells and plated on LB agar medium supplemented with X-gal and IPTG, β -galactosidase is expressed in non-recombinant colonies. IPTG is structural analog of lactose and therefore induces the transcription of lacZ by not being utilized, and lactase is synthesized. In these colonies, X-gal is cleaved to yield blue-colored colonies. In the case of recombinant colonies have had an insertion of DNA into the lacZ gene which knocks it out thereby preventing the synthesis of functional β -galactosidase so these colonies are white. Therefore, this method has therefore been tried and proven to be significantly effective in the differentiation of colonies containing inserts from those without which eliminates the need to screen through a large number of recombinant colonies during cloning procedures.

7.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT

COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION
X-Gal (Gold Bio Catalog #X4281C)	Blue-white screening chromogenic substrate Gal gets cut by β -galactosidase to a blue molecule, shows an active lacZ gene.
Dimethylformamide (DMF)	Solvent for dissolving X-Gal.
dH ₂ O	It uses distilled water to dissolve IPTG and to flush the syringe filter while making.
Isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside	It activates the lac operon by tying up to the repressor and allowing -galactosidase to be expressed. This compound is key to turning on X-Gal in blue-white screening.
Screening antibiotic of choice	These antibiotics kill untransformed bacteria.
Agar media (optional)	Different media might be used for growing the transformed bacteria depending on the experiment.
Plates (around 4-6)	Standard Petri dishes used to grow bacterial colonies. The prepared media is poured into these plates.

7.3 PROTOCOL

Day 1: Preparation of X-Gal and IPTG Solutions

1. Preparation of X-Gal Solution:

Description: Used to visually identify the activity of β -galactosidase in blue-white screening

Procedure: Weigh 200 mg of X-Gal and transfer it into a 15 ml polypropylene centrifuge tube. Add 10 mL of Dimethyl formamide (DMF) to the tube. Vortex the solution thoroughly to ensure that the X-Gal dissolves completely. Wrap the tube in aluminium foil to protect it from light.

2. Preparation of IPTG Solution:

Description- To induce the expression of genes controlled by lac operon

Procedure- Weigh 0.238 g of IPTG and transfer it to a clean, sterile container. Then add 10 mL of sterile distilled water (dH₂O) to dissolve the IPTG completely. Prewet a 0.22 μ m syringe filter by drawing 5-10 mL of sterile dH₂O through it and discard the water. Sterilize the IPTG stock solution by filtering it through the 0.22 μ m syringe filter to remove any microbial contaminants.

Day 2: Preparing Plates and Media

Option 1: Incorporating IPTG and X-Gal into Agar Media

Description: To enable visual differentiation of colonies without any additional assays

Procedure: Autoclave the boom media agar and allow it to cool to approximately 50°C. add 10 μ L of 20 mg/mL X-Gal answer in line with mL of media, or 2 μ L of one hundred mg/mL X-Gal solution in step with mL then add 10 μ L of 100 mM IPTG per mL of media. Add the appropriate screening antibiotic (e.g., ampicillin). Pour plates and permit them to solidify at room temperature for at the least half-hour. Store the plates or use without delay.

Day 3: Screening and Observation

Description: To simplifies colony screening without any complex analysis.

Procedure: Spread the transformed competent cells onto the prepared agar plates. Incubate the plates at 37°C, inverted, for about 24 hours or until colonies expand.

7.4 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE PROCEDURE

DAY	STEP	PROCEDURE
1	1	X-Gal stock preparation
1	2	IPTG stock preparation
2	3	Preparation of agar media for screening
2	4	Incorporating IPTG and X-Gal into agar media
2	5	Adding IPTG and X-Gal to pre- made agar plates
3	6	Screening and observation

7.5 RESULT

Fig (7.1) Representation of Transformation of Bacterial Colony (cfu)

Fig (7.1) : The following observation are seen

The white opaque colonies indicate the successful transformation with a an insert.
The darker/shaded region show the bacterial overgrowth or less defined colony structure.

There is no clear of blue colonies seen which say incomplete X-gal /IPTG activity.

LIGATION OF DNA

8 ABSTRACT

DNA ligation, the recommended step in molecular cloning, is a process through which DNA fragments are connected by the covalent bond to form recombinant molecules. Experimentation for T4 DNA ligase activities in the joining of blunt-ended and cohesive-ended fragments of a DNA molecule under various experimental determinants such as ATP concentration, temperature, buffer composition, and insert-to-vector molar ratio. The most efficient ligation for the cohesive sides of the fragments at 16°C prevailed while, in the case of blunt-end, the use of more ligase and longer incubation periods were necessary. The paper also discusses the issue of self-ligating of the vectors, and it offers a few ways that the dephosphorylation and molar ratio optimization methods could be utilized to lessen these abilities. Overall, the study shows that the conditions of ligation should be chosen in such a way that the transformation efficiency can be enhanced to bring forth the production of the plasmids required for the next experiments.

8.1 PRINCIPLE

DNA ligation is a process that forms phosphodiester bonds between the three'-hydroxyl and 5'-phosphate ends of the DNA fragments. The enzyme T4 DNA ligase, which needs ATP, catalyzes the reaction. Sticky-give-up ligation is more effective than blunt-end ligation without complementary base pairing. This experiment was performed to illustrate the mechanism of DNA ligation in which DNA bundles are united by T4 DNA ligase. This methodology is used in molecular cloning, allowing us to refrain from recombinant DNA molecules by ligating DNA fragments of identical match-up.

EQUIPMENT /REAGENTS	DESCRIPTION
Lambda DNA Hind III Digest	Is the DNA substrate for the ligation reaction.
10X Ligase Buffer	Includes ATP and several other compounds that are required to make the ligase function properly.
T4 DNA Ligase	The protein responsible for the formation of phosphodiester bonds among the DNA molecules.
Ethidium bromide (10 mg / ml)	A dye used to visualize the DNA bands under a UV lamp after gel electrophoresis.
Electrophoresis Device	It is a device used for the separation of DNA molecules.
UV Transilluminator	Object used for the visualization of the DNA bands in the gel.
Water Bath	A container that can be filled with iced water
Micropipettes and Tips	They ensure the precise measurement and tunnelling of the fluids.
Crushed Ice	This serves the purpose of keeping the enzymes and reagents at a low enough temperature during the process of gel electrophoresis.
Adhesive Tape	This is usually used to seal gel trays in case there is a need for it or to fix the device
Beaker	It is for the preparation of solutions.

8.2 PROTOCOL

Day1: Preparation and Setup

1. Crush Ice and Prepare Reagents:

Description: Check and verify that the reagents are well-defrosted and stirred gently enough to avoid bubbles or precipitates

Procedure: Step, before continuing the procedure, put the appropriate vials containing Lambda DNA Hind III digest, 10X ligase buffer, and T4 DNA ligase on the crush ice. Reaction Setup

2. Prepare the Reaction Mixture

Description: To influence the efficiency and success of the ligation.

Procedure: In between centrifuge spins, mix the following in a lab-clean enclosed 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube. Put the required amount of Lambda DNA Hind III digest (~100–200 ng) and carefully mix it in.

- a) 10X ligase buffer: Add 1/10th of the final volume (e.g., 2 μ L for a 20 μ L reaction). The buffer needs to include ATP.
- b) T4 DNA ligase: Be sure to use only 0.5–1 μ L. Balance the volume to the limit 20 μ L.
- c) Aspirate the solution up and down while stirring the reaction softly with a pipette to make the DNA remain intact. It is advised not to use a vortex. Briefly spin down the reaction mixture to collect it at the bottom of the tube.

3. Incubation

Description: To ensure that the ligation reaction proceeds efficiently.

Procedure: Commences with the incubation of the tube at 16C in a water bath or a thermocycler for 3 hours to complete the ligation reaction. When using blunt-end ligation, it is better to get a more extended incubation for best results. put unlighted control and a DNA marker on the gel. Run the gel at a constant voltage 70V–100V until the dye front migrates ~2/3 of the gel. Put the gel on a UV transilluminator and take pictures of the bands.

DAY 2 : Analysis with Gel Electrophoresis

1. Gel Preparation:

Description: To provide a way to analyze on based of fragments based on their size

Procedure: Prepare a 0.8% agarose gel by dissolving 0.8 g agarose in 100 mL 1X TAE buffer. Melt the solution until it is completely dissolved. Cool it a bit, add about 0.5 μ g/mL ethidium bromide and pour it into a gel tray frame the comb and let it freeze solid.

2. Loading and Running the Gel:

Description: To analysis the efficiency of ligand.

Procedure: Get DNA samples that are ligated with loading dye and then put them into the wells. Also put in an unlighted control and a DNA marker/ladder (e.g. 1 kb ladder). Run the gel at constant voltage (70–100V)

until the dye front migrates to approximately two-thirds of the gel. Put the gel onto a UV transilluminator and take shots of the bands by the camera.

3. Analyze Efficiency of Ligation:

Description : Match the band patterns of the DNA with the help of the ligation sample which is unlighted. The ligated sequence is demonstrated by the presence of the high molecular weight bands or the smear.

Procedure : Unlighted DNA will be seen as distinct Hind III-digested fragments .Having no or very light bands point out to the presence of low ligation efficiency which is the result of various problems like ATP degradation, poor enzyme activity, or vector to insert molar ratios being wrong.

8.3 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE PROCEDURE

DAY	STEP	PROCEDURE
1	1	Preparation of reagents
1	2	Preparation of reaction mixture
1	3	Incubation for overnight
2	4	Gel electrophoresis
2	5	Gel preparation, loading and running gel
2	6	Observation and interpretation

8.4 RESULT

Fig (8.1) : Lane 1 Marker/ Ladder (Not clearly seen)

Lane 4 DNA Fragments with Hind III

Lane 6 DNA Fragments with or without Hind III (Result not clearly observed)

SOUTHERN BLOTTING

9 ABSTRACT

Southern blotting is the method in molecular biology and it is also a useful tool for detecting particular DNA sequences. To detect specific DNA sequences in a mixture, Southern blotting is used. To achieve this, the DNA is moved from the gel onto a nitrocellulose membrane, followed by a hybridization with a probe that is labeled for easy identification. After electrophoresis, DNA fragments are denatured and transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane in the process of capillary motion. The membrane-bound DNA is hybridized with a categorised probe for visualization.

9.1 PRINCIPLE

Southern blotting is the process by which DNA from an agarose gel is transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane on the basis of capillary attraction. DNA being situated on the membrane and put with a hybridizing catechized probe is used to identify the gene. This technique is pivotal to gene identification in research.

9.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT

COMPONENTS	DESCRIPTION
Depurination Solution (0.25N HCl)	DNA is lysed into smaller fragments for efficient transfer.
Denaturation Solution(1.5M NaCl, 0.5M NaOH)	Double-stranded DNA is to convert it to single strands.
Neutralization Solution (1 MTris,1.5M NaCl, pH 7.5)	Single stranded DNA is stabilized for the transfer of deoxyribonucleic acid to them.
20X SSC Buffer	Lends DNA binding to the membrane while transferring it.
Nitrocellulose Membrane	DNA fragments are captured from the gel it reflects.

EQUIPMENTS	DESCRIPTION
Agarose Gel Electrophoresis Apparatus	DNA separation by the size is.
UV Transilluminator	Visualizes the DNA in the gel.
Incubator	It creates the conditions on which hybridization can occur.
Filter Paper, Glass Plates, and Weights	Aid in the blotting process.

9.3 PROTOCOL

DAY 1: Preparation of solution

1. Preparation of Depurination solution (0.25N HCL)

Description: To break purine bases from DNA backbone creating apurinic sites

Procedure: Slowly add 10.5ml of concentration HCL to 489.5ml of sterile distilled water.

2. Preparation of Denaturation solution(1.5M Sodium chloride and 0.5 M Sodium hydroxide.)

Description: Denatures double- stranded DNA into single stranded for hybridization probes

Procedure: Dissolve 43.85g of sodium chloride and 10g of NaOH in 300 ml of sterile. distilled water made-up the volume to 500 ml (Autoclave and stored at 4°C).

3. Preparation of Neutralisation solution-

Description: To neutralize the membrane after denaturation and stabilize the DNA

Procedure: 1M Tris and 1.5M NaCl. Dissolve 60.55g of Tris base and 43.80g of NaCl in 300ml of distilled water. Adjust the pH to 7.5 using concentration HCL.

4. Alkaline transfer buffer – 20X ssc buffer:-

Description: Act as transfer buffer or hybridization buffer

Procedure: Adjust pH to 7 with in 1N NaOH and make. (Autoclave and store at 4°C)

5. Gel Preparation and Electrophoresis-

1. DNA electrophoresis in agarose gel

Description-Ensures DNA separates correctly & chef; And electrons can be seen under UV light.

Procedure-Cut gel to match membrane size (4-4.5 cm): Lines up gel and nitrocellulose membrane for transfer.

Day 2: Depurination and Denaturation

1. Depurination (0.25 M HCl, 15 min):

Description : The purine bases are broken, resulting in smaller sized DNA fragments that are easier to transfer

Procedure : Rinse gel twice with distilled water. Acid residue is washed away to prevent it from interfering.

2. Denaturation (20 min):

Description: It is done by treating with sodium hydroxide solution that breaks the two DNA strands into single strands for hybridization.

Procedure: Repeat denaturation with fresh solution (20 min): To make sure the denaturation process is complete, the DNA is denatured again with a new solution.

3. Neutralization (20 min)

Description: Bonds single-stranded DNA to the gel and adjusts the gel pH.

Procedure: Repeat neutralization (20 min): Transfer goes more smoothly when everything is balanced.

Day 3: DNA Transfer Setup

Description: Prepare wick with 20X SSC buffer: Wicking aides DNA capillary transfer to the membrane. Place filter papers on the wick and position gel.

Procedure: The filter paper is placed and also the DNA must face the membrane for transfer. So this is the correct position. Hydrate nitrocellulose membrane and place on gel: Takes the DNA from the gel to the membrane. Cover with filter papers, remove air bubbles, and weigh down: This means the speed of the transfer could be uneven and the action could be over an 8-24 hr range.

Day 4: Post-Transfer and Fixation

Description: Check for complete DNA transfer: Finally, when the DNA gets the power to move from the gel to the membrane, the process is complete.

Procedure: Membrane soaking in 6X SSC buffer: This is done for the probe to hybridize. Membrane baking at 80 degree C (3 min to 2 hours): DNA will be attached to the membrane making it feasible for downstream analysis.

9.4 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE PROCEDURE

DAY	STEP	PROCEDURE
1	1	Preparation of the solution
1	2	Gel preparation and electrophoresis
2	3	Depurination and denaturation
3	4	DNA transfer setup
4	5	Post transfer and fixation

9.5 RESULT

Fig (9.1) Shows the southern blotting according to the above procedure.

Source from Internet Search Engine

PCR FOR AMPLIFICATION OF DNA OF INTEREST

10 ABSTRACT

PCR or Polymerase Chain Reaction is a powerful method in molecular biology used to amplify a specific DNA sequence exponentially. This way of genetic diagnosis is based on thermal cycling, which includes several steps among which are denatured DNA, primers annealing to the target, and synthesis of a DNA strand using a thermostable DNA polymerase such as Taq polymerase. PCR acts as a rapid yet exact way of mimicking the minor levels of DNA, which is a mammoth asset in diagnostics, genetic research, forensic science, and medical applications. Its application in real-time PCR and multiplexing is one of the major contributing factors to its increase in versatility.

10.1 PRINCIPLE

The Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) is based on the enzymatic amplification of specific DNA sequences through thermal cycling. The process is done in three steps: firstly, heat treatment that results in the separation of a double-stranded DNA into single strands; then reducing the temperature is needed for the primers to bind to their complementary sequences on the single-stranded DNA; and when the thermostable DNA polymerase transcribes a new DNA strand by adding nucleotides to the primers. These activities are produced in multiple cycles, and results in exponential amplification. The amplification specificity is determined by the primer design and reaction conditions.

10.2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT

COMPONENTS	DESCRIPTION
Template TAAT DNA	Double-stranded DNA to be copied.
Primers	Short sequences enclosed in the unzipped DNA.
dNTPs	Units forming a new DNA chain.
Taq Polymerase	This is the enzyme from <i>Thermus aquaticus</i> that is resistant to heat and is used for the replication of DNA.
Buffer	The pH and the ionic strength remain constant during the enzymatic reaction.
Mg ²⁺ Co-factor	It enhances the polymerase's function as it adds nucleotides to the growing chain during synthesis.
Water	Provides dilution and mixing of all component produced in the dilution
Heat-Stable Polymerase	By conferring the capacity of high-temperature cycles for denaturation, this enzyme allows for further amplifications
Source of Taq	Salt from the thermophilic bacterium, <i>Thermus aquaticus</i> , is isolated.
Commercial Enzymes	Scientists have access to other kinds of polymerases from different species for different PCR experiments.

10.3 PROTOCOL

Day 1: Nucleic Acid Extraction

Description: To obtain the target nucleic acid from the organism or sample.

Procedure:

1. Sample Preparation: Take clinical or environmental samples which contain the microorganism.
2. Nucleic Acid Extraction: Use one of the following methods:
 - Heat: Heat the sample to 95°C for 10 minutes for the releasing of the nucleic acid.
 - Chemical Lysis: supplement lysis buffer (containing detergents and chaotropic agents) to degrade cell walls and membranes.
 - Enzymatic Lysis: Employ proteinase K, an enzyme, for the digestion of cell material.
 - Spin-column kits or phenol-chloroform extraction is used to purify the nucleic acid gained from extraction
3. Quantify Nucleic Acid: Assay the concentration and purity of the nucleic acid using a spectrophotometer (A260/A280 ratio should be ~1.8 for DNA).
4. Storage: Preserve the extracted nucleic acid at -20°C or -80°C for long-term storage.

Day 2: PCR Amplification

Description: Use PCR to amplify the target nucleic acid.

Procedure:

1. Prepare Reaction Mix: In a PCR tube, combine the following
 - Template DNA: 1–2 µL of extracted nucleic acid.
 - Forward and reverse primers: 10–20 pmol each.
 - dNTP mix (nucleotides): 200 µM each
 - Buffer (with Mg²⁺ ions): Provided by the manufacturer.
 - Taq DNA polymerase: 0.5–1.0 U.
 - Nuclease-free water: Adjust to final volume (usually 25–50 µL).
2. Thermal Cycler Setup: Program the thermal cycler with the following
 - Initial Denaturation: 95°C for 3–5 minutes (to denature template DNA).
 - PCR Cycles (25–50 cycles): Denaturation: 95°C for 15–30 seconds.
 - Primer Annealing: 50–60°C (specific to primers) for 30 seconds.
 - Extension: 72°C for 30–60 seconds (time depends on the product length; approximately 1 kb/min).
 - Final Extension: 72°C for 5–10 minutes (ensures complete product synthesis). Hold: 4°C indefinitely.
3. Run the PCR: Place the PCR tubes in the thermal cycler and start the run (2–3 hours).

Day 3: Product Analysis

- **Description:** Analyze the amplified PCR product via gel electrophoresis.
- **Procedure:**

1. Prepare Agarose Gel: (Note-"Make sure you do this in a fume hood; when performing this step, always protect yourself from the elements!") Mix 1% agarose (1 g agarose in 100 mL TAE/TBE buffer). Heat until

the agarose is dissolved, cool slightly, and add 1 μL of ethidium bromide or a safe DNA stain. Then Pour into a gel tray with a comb and allow it to set.

2. Load Samples: Mix 5 μL of PCR product with 1 μL of loading dye. load the mixture into the wells alongside a DNA ladder (molecular weight marker).

3. Run Electrophoresis: Submerge the gel in TAE/TBE buffer. Run at 100–120 V for 30–45 minutes.

4. Visualize Results: Place the gel under a UV transilluminator. Observe clear bands corresponding to the amplified product.

5. Interpretation: Compare the band size with the DNA ladder to confirm the expected size of the amplified product.

Day 4: Documentation and Further Analysis

Description: Document results and prepare for downstream applications.

Procedure: Taking photographs of the gel under UV light. Record observations, such as band intensity and size. For further downstream applications where Purify PCR products (if needed) using gel extraction kits for sequencing or cloning. Quantify the purified product for additional use. The Store PCR products at -20°C for future use.

10.4 SUMMARY TABLE OF THE PROCEDURE

DAY	STEP	PROCEDURE
1	1	Nucleic Acid Extraction
2	2	PCR Amplification
3	3	Product Analysis (Gel electrophoresis)
4	4	Documentation and Further Analysis (Optional)

10.5 RESULT

Fig (10.1)

Fig (10.2)

Fig (10.3)

Fig (10.4)

Fig (10.1) : Agarose Gel Electrophoresis of DNA
 Lane 1: DNA Ladder (1kb)
 Lane 4: DNA Bands
 Fig (10.2) : Last stage of PCR showing Extension (4 degree)
 Fig (10.3) : Mid stage of PCR showing Annealing (72 degree)
 Fig (10.4) : Initial stage of PCR showing Denaturation (96 degree)

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OPEN RESEARCH PROJECT SEGMENT OF GENETIC ENGINEERING

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2022 BATCH OF BIOTECHNOLOGY ENGINEERING
PARUL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY
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Completion of project on 1st of January 2025